

Linking values to actions for wild pollinator conservation: perspectives in Europe

Zafarani Uwingabire^{1,2*}, Aiora Zabala³, Nibedita Mukherjee⁴, and Juliette C. Young¹

¹*Université de Bourgogne Europe, Institut Agro Dijon, INRAE, UMR Agroécologie, Dijon, France*

²*Université de Bourgogne Europe, Institut Agro Dijon, INRAE, UMR CESAER, Dijon, France*

³*Cambridge Centre for Environment, Energy and Natural Resource Governance, Department of Land Economy, University of Cambridge, The David Attenborough Building, Pembroke Street, Cambridge, CB2 3QZ, U.K.*

⁴*Division of Anthropology, Geography and Development, Department of Social and Political Sciences, Brunel University, London, UK*

* Corresponding author email address : zafarani.uwingabire@agrosupdijon.fr

Keywords: Q methodology; biodiversity valuation; ecosystem services; nature's contributions to people; plural values

Abstract

Pollinator declines challenge societal values and priorities in Europe. This study captures how such values intersect with policy preferences. We examine diverse perspectives of key stakeholder groups from business, policy, research and NGOs in Europe to investigate the underlying value systems and motivations that can drive pollinator conservation actions. The identified perspectives reveal variation in how individuals understand pollinators, their perception on pollinator values and how they conceptualise (ir)relevant pollinator conservation responses. This offers a more nuanced understanding of the sociocultural drivers of biodiversity management. While all perspectives acknowledged the importance of pollinator conservation to some extent, they diverge in the values they prioritize and the actions they support. Perspectives on actions differed in how they conceptualised the role of governance

and authority — ranging from moral obligations to protect all species, to instrumental arguments for maintaining pollination functions. Correlations between different perspectives on values and actions show distinct patterns. Those with relationship-centred values (focused on balancing social needs) tended to prefer top-down regulations. Nature-centred intrinsic values (focused on ethical considerations) supported both alternative technical solutions and bottom-up awareness efforts. A perspective emphasizing all-species equality favoured top-down regulations and opposed horizontal coordination and collaboration. In contrast, those with human-centred values (highlighting the benefits of pollinators for food production and ecosystem services) preferred non-intervention and supported horizontal collaboration. Discussion highlights implications for the design, legitimacy, and transformative potential of conservation initiatives.

Highlights

1. Relationship-centred values are associated with support for top-down regulations.
2. Nature-centred intrinsic values support both technical solutions and bottom-up awareness raising efforts.
3. An all-species equality perspective favours top-down regulation and opposes horizontal coordination.
4. Human-centred values are linked to preference for non-intervention and support for horizontal collaboration.
5. Accounting for value diversity within stakeholder groups can strengthen the legitimacy and effectiveness of pollinator conservation policies.

1. Introduction

The ongoing loss of wild pollinator biodiversity (bees, flies, butterflies and other groups) represents not only an ecological crisis but also a profound challenge to societal values and priorities in Europe. As pollinators vanish under mounting anthropogenic pressures — including habitat degradation, pesticide use, and climate change — essential services they provide like ecosystem stability, agricultural productivity, and food security are placed at risk (Vanbergen et al., 2013; Lautenbach et al., 2012; Potts et al., 2016; Uwingabire & Gallai, 2024).

In response, conservation efforts have increasingly focussed on ecosystem service (ES) valuation to inform policies aimed at reversing this decline (e.g. the ES and Nature's Contributions to People (NCP) frameworks; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005; IPBES, 2016, 2019). The instrumental and intrinsic values of pollinators — emphasizing human-centred and nature-centred worldviews respectively — underpin dominant valuation frameworks that resonate with European institutions and related actors (Agnolletti & Emanuelli, 2016; van den Born et al., 2001). Such valuations build on approaches typically grounded in rational calculations, which prioritizes measurable outcomes using quantifiable indicators and universal metrics to guide policy efficiently (Scott, 2000), but often neglect relational values, the meaningfulness of human-nature interactions, rooted in identity, culture, care, and moral responsibility (Klain et al., 2017; Chan et al., 2018). Yet, while decision-making processes grounded in logic, objectivity, and systematic analysis may align with institutional goals, they resonate less with individual stakeholders (Simon, 1976). Indeed, while these perspectives may have helped elevate pollinator conservation on policy agendas in Europe (e.g. the [EU Nature Restoration Law](#) Regulation (EU) 2024/1991, art. 10 “Restoration of pollinator populations”) there is still an implementation struggle to drive needed change on the ground (Dupré et al., 2021; Marselle et al., 2021). Thus, focusing only on values of pollinators for society or for nature raises critical questions about the adequacy of dichotomous frameworks in capturing the deeper relational dimensions of human-nature connections (Muradian and Gomez-Baggethun, 2021). As pollinator conservation moves from science into political and

societal discourse, it becomes crucial to explore how diverse stakeholder worldviews and values, grounded in differing value systems, could be better integrated to shape the way we understand and act to prevent the ongoing loss of wild pollinators (IPBES, 2022).

From this view, conservation is not solely an economic or ecological imperative; it also embodies values such as care, moral responsibility, and stewardship. This paper builds on studies highlighting the complexity of human–nature relationships, as emphasized by the IPBES (2024) report, which calls for inclusive valuation approaches that reflect diverse worldviews and values in decision-making (Lo and Spash, 2013; Jax et al., 2018; Chan et al., 2016). We build on Uwingabire et al. (2025) that highlights the importance of moving beyond strictly human- or nature-centred worldviews in pollinator management to encompass moral, relational, and socio-cultural dimensions in pollinator conservation. This study emphasises the growing significance of relationship-centred worldviews in shaping actions toward pollinator conservation in Europe — perspectives that extend concerns not only to present human needs but also to future generations, pollinators irreplaceability, and nature as a whole. However, a critical gap remains in understanding the link between worldviews, values and actions, which is essential for developing more inclusive, context-sensitive, and effective conservation actions.

To address this gap, we analyse the diversity of worldviews and values of key European stakeholders on pollinators, and explore individuals' opinions regarding policy actions. We adopt a pluralistic value framework and examine how diverse worldviews and values may affect opinions towards pollinator conservation actions. Recognising these linkages can inform transformative conservation actions. By foregrounding context-specific, diverse perspectives and integrating them into conservation, this approach offers a pathway toward more inclusive, socially legitimate, and effective conservation actions — one that acknowledges both the tangible values of pollinators and the deeper, often unquantifiable reasons (relations, ethics, care) that drive individuals and communities to act. Specifically, we address the following research questions, focusing on European contexts:

Q1. What areas of consensus and divergence emerge among key stakeholder worldviews and values on pollinators?

Q2. What are the main actions aimed at pollinator conservation that key stakeholders regard as (un)important or (ir)relevant?

Q3. What is the association between worldviews, values and actions and how can we build on this to improve pollinator conservation?

2. Materials and methods

To address these questions, we use Q-methodology, a semi-quantitative approach that captures and analyses the diversity of subjective viewpoints on a topic of concern (Stephenson, 1953; Brown, 1980; Watts & Stenner, 2012). This method allows for the systematic identification and categorisation of diverse perspectives by asking participants to rank and sort a series of statements. By doing so, we reveal the underlying value systems and motivations that can drive pollinator conservation actions, offering a more nuanced understanding of the sociocultural drivers of biodiversity management.

We followed the structured four-stage approach outlined by Zabala et al. (2018): 1) research design, 2) data collection, 3) analysis, and 4) interpretation.

Stage 1. Research design

We constructed a comprehensive set of statements based on a previously published paper by Uwingabire et al. (2025). This paper used semi-structured interviews to explore the different worldviews and values concerning pollinators and their conservation among key stakeholders in business, research, policymaking, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) across Europe, including minority views. Interviewees were selected based on their direct or indirect roles in pollinator diversity conservation or their influence on pressures affecting biodiversity in Europe.

The initial set of statements was analysed to identify recurring themes, ensuring a broad representation of viewpoints. The final selection of statements for the double Q-sort exercise was categorised into two subtopics: i) Q-set on worldviews and values – perspectives on the role and importance of pollinators and other values related to pollinators (Table 1); and ii) Q-set on actions – perceptions of effective conservation strategies (Table 2). During the process of sampling the Q-set, we eliminated and merged redundant sentences iteratively and reformulated statements in a more comprehensive active form, as standard. A balanced subset of statements from both subtopics was selected for ranking by respondents in the Q-sort process.

Each of the 38 statements for the Q-set on worldviews is aligned with one of three worldviews categories: human-centred, nature-centred, and relationships-centred worldviews (Table 1, Uwingabire et al., 2025). Respondents sorted the full statements, and short statements are provided here to facilitate the communication of results.

Table 1. Q-sort I: worldviews and values of and about pollinators. Participants sorted statements from most agreement to most disagreement.

N	Short statements	Full statements
		Human-centred
1.	Human domination	Humans have the right to rule over other life forms.
2.	Pesticide necessity	It is necessary to use pesticides/herbicides in agriculture to meet food demands of the world's growing population.
3.	Wind pollination	No one is going to starve due to wild pollinator decline because the majority of food crops are wind pollinated.
4.	Honeybee alt.	Wild pollinators can be replaced by managed honeybees to pollinate our crops.
5.	Tech alt.	New technologies like robot bees could solve any problems with pollinator declines.
6.	Yield improvement	Wild pollinators play a vital role in improving crop yield.
7.	Yield maintenance	Wild pollinators are important to maintain stable crop yields over time.
8.	Food variety	There will be less variety of food available if pollinators decline.
9.	Nutrition	Without wild pollinators, essential nutritious food like fruits and vegetables will be short in supply.
10.	Price increase	Without wild pollinators, prices of nutritious food like fruits and vegetables will increase.
11.	Seed maintenance	Wild pollinators play an important role in the maintenance of seed production.
12.	Aesthetics	Wild pollinators increase landscape aesthetics by pollinating wild flowers.
13.	Cultural benefits	Cultural benefits of wild pollinators, such as butterfly recording and pollinator-friendly gardening, are important to people.
14.	Competitiveness	Safeguarding wild pollinators in Europe will make European farmers uncompetitive because the same standards are not required for food products imported from outside Europe.
		Nature-centred
15.	Egalitarian	Humans have the same importance as everything else on earth.
16.	Physical limits	There are physical limits to economic growth on the planet.
17.	Impact on other life	Without wild pollinators, other forms of life will be deeply affected.
18.	Normal extinction	It is normal that some wild pollinator species go extinct.
19.	Morality	It is a moral responsibility of humanity to care for wild pollinators.
20.	Complexity	Humans don't understand much of the complex roles that wild pollinators play in nature.
21.	Own right	Wild pollinators are important in their own right.
22.	Usefulness	Wild pollinators don't have to be useful for humans in order to be protected.
23.	Precaution	The consequences of a full-blown pollinator collapse are so huge that we should not even run the risk of this happening.
24.	Impact plants and animals	Wild pollinators should be protected because they sustain many plants and animals.
		Relationship-centred

25.	Separability	Treating nature as something separate from people is dangerous.
26.	Part of nature	Humans cannot have a negative effect on nature because they are themselves part of nature.
27.	Difficult life	Humans may not kill life on planet earth but they will make life much more difficult.
28.	(Re)connect	Wild pollinators are important for people to (re)connect with nature.
29.	Wellbeing	Wild pollinators contribute to our physical, mental and spiritual wellbeing.
30.	Food habits	People should change their food habits to encourage less farm intensification.
31.	Food waste	If food waste is reduced there will be enough food to feed the world without pesticides/herbicides.
32.	Financial benefits	A society can function without constantly making financial benefits.
33.	Tech illusion	Hoping that all problems will be fixed through new technology is a mistake.
34.	Future generations	Respecting wild pollinators can remind us of our responsibility to future generations.
35.	Artificial vs real	Seeing an artificial bee does not give humans the same kind of happiness as a real bee.
36.	Tech non-alt.	Alternatives to wild pollinators (robots, managed honeybees, etc.) will not prevent the ecological damage caused by the loss of wild pollinators.
37.	Lack of data	There is not enough data about wild pollinator decline to inform decisions about their conservation.
38.	Oblivious	I am not seeing the consequences of wild pollinator decline in my everyday life.

The 40 statements for Q-set on actions are aligned into various themes including pesticides ban, regulations, conditioned (or not) incentives and subsidies, tax schemes, habitat creation, restoration and management, raising awareness, knowledge and capacity building, collaboration and cross-sector cooperation (Dicks et al., 2021).

Table 2. Q-set on pollinator conservation actions. Participants sorted statements from most effective to least effective

No	Short statements	Full statements
1.	Precaution law	It is important to protect wild pollinators because we don't know all the consequences of their decline.
2.	Food distribution	To feed the world, improving food distribution is more important than intensifying agriculture.
3.	Nature everywhere	Nature is needed everywhere: in managed spaces, in natural spaces and in urban spaces.
4.	Connected habitats	Unless natural habitats are connected to each other there is no point in protecting wild pollinators.
5.	Less meat	People should change their diet by eating less meat.
6.	Seasonal foods	People should change their diet by eating seasonal foods.
7.	Pesticide ban	Pesticides that are harmful to wild pollinators should be banned.
8.	Pesticide reduction	Pesticides that are harmful to wild pollinators should be used a lot less often than they currently are.
9.	Nat. pest control	We should use natural pest control that increases wild pollinator numbers.
10.	Safer pesticides	Industries need to develop pesticides that are safer for humans, other species and the environment.
11.	Training	Subsidies should be connected to compulsory training to inform farmers about the best way to support wild pollinators.
12.	Inspections	There should be more on-farm inspections to check that farmers use pesticides safely for wild pollinators.
13.	Bio-security	Bio-security awareness is needed to avoid the introduction of non-native species that can negatively affect wild pollinators.
14.	Research	Research activities should be redirected from maximizing yield to nature-friendly agriculture.
15.	Agroforestry	There is a need for more agroforestry (systems where trees and crops are grown on the same land) to support wild pollinators.
16.	Internalising	Governments urgently need to ensure that the full impacts of the production of goods and services on nature are included in their price (internalising externalities).
17.	Harmful subsidies	Cutting out subsidies harmful to wild pollinators is the single most important action to conserve them.
18.	Honeybees	Measures that benefit honeybees also benefit wild pollinators.
19.	Gov. investment	More government investment is needed to implement scientific recommendations for wild pollinators protection.
20.	Private-public coordination	Actions to protect wild pollinators need to be better co-ordinated between businesses and public agencies.
21.	Transversality	When evaluating applications for any urban or agricultural land-use, the conservation of wild pollinators should be considered.
22.	Monitoring tech	Technology innovation (e.g., camera traps, AI) to monitor the presence of wild pollinator on a farm is needed.
23.	Seed mixes	Farmers should be provided with seed mixes of wild plants to bring back biodiversity in the landscape.

24.	Science	Advancing the science is the only way to achieve wild pollinator conservation.
25.	Lack of capacity	The main impediment for a stronger implementation of wild pollinator conservation policies is lack of capacity in managing wild pollinator habitats.
26.	Legal frameworks	Translation of the Common Agricultural Policy into different legal frameworks and regulations by Member States should prioritise wild pollinator conservation purposes.
27.	People power	More people should be encouraged to set up their own projects to protect wild pollinators.
28.	Econ valuation	It is crucial to measure the economic impact of the link between wild pollinators and the pollination service they deliver.
29.	Governance levels	Wild pollinator conservation needs to be addressed at all governance levels: at EU, national, regional and local level.
30.	Polluter pays	The law should oblige industries to compensate heavily for the consequences of their activities on nature.
31.	Pesticide suppliers	Pesticide suppliers should pay for wild pollinator restoration schemes.
32.	Urban information	Cities administrations should inform citizens about which plants and management practices of green spaces are best for wild pollinators.
33.	Awareness	Government should aim to raise people's awareness about wild pollinators through education.
34.	Incentives	Government should create financial incentives for farmers to implement wild pollinator-friendly farming.
35.	Collaboration	More collaboration between stakeholders on wild pollinator conservation – from discussions to actions – is crucial.
36.	Beekeeper ambassador	Every beekeeper should be an ambassador for wild pollinators.
37.	Coordinated governments	Governments at different levels must work together to coordinate the implementation of wild pollinator-friendly policies.
38.	Imports	The European Commission should ensure that wild pollinator-friendly practices are considered in imported products.
39.	No greenwashing	Businesses should be held accountable for what they communicate about nature protection (to prevent greenwashing).
40.	'Unfair' regulations	It is 'unfair' to place wild pollinator regulations on European industries as the same standards are not required on imported products.

Stage 2. Data Collection

The data collection phase included participant sampling and Q-sorting. Participants were chosen based on a stakeholder mapping exercise conducted within the H2020 Safeguard Project (Kinneen et al., 2022), which identified key actors from academia, NGOs, and think tanks, including contributors to the IPBES Pollination Assessment (IPBES, 2016). Instead of a statistically representative sample, the participant sampling strategy aimed to include respondents with diverse views or likely to hold differing perspectives (Zabala et al., 2018). Of 276 key stakeholders contacted for the study, 38 participants completed both Q-sorts as required (Sample's summary statistics with values of variability and further details can be found in the supplementary material Table S.1; Table S.2). The final sample comprised 12 females and 26 males, with representation from Northern (n = 5), Southern (n = 5), Eastern (n = 10), and Western Europe (n = 18) (see Supplementary Material, Table S.1). Educational attainment was relatively homogeneous, with 72% of participants holding a Ph.D. or equivalent and 26% holding a Master's degree. This reflects the composition of existing European science – policy networks on pollinators, which predominantly involve highly educated experts. Participants were primarily researchers (60%), policymakers (16%), business representatives (14%), and

professionals from non-governmental organizations (10%). This purposive sampling strategy was designed to ensure a well-rounded foundation for analysing the diverse perspectives on pollinator conservation discussed in the subsequent sections.

Each participant sorted the statements from those they most agreed with (or found most significant) to those they least agreed with (or found least significant). Respectively, the Q-sort on worldviews and values and on actions were presented to participants as follows. First, participants were asked to group statements in three groups, according to whether they disagreed with them, they agreed, and the rest. Second, they ranked the statements in a column-based grid, implicitly scoring each item and allowing for quantitative analysis (Subiza-Pérez et al., 2023). This forced-choice distribution encourages participants to make nuanced judgments about each statement's relative importance (Watts & Stenner, 2012). Finally, qualitative explanations after each respondent sorted the items was requested to explain why they agreed most or disagreed most with the statements they had placed at the extremes of the grid.

The data collection phase began with six pilot tests to refine the Q-sorting process and ensure clarity in the statements and methodology. Three tests were first conducted face-to-face and then three were conducted online to maximise the feedback that allowed us further refinements where needed. This phase ensured that the collected data captured a diverse range of perspectives on pollinator conservation, setting the foundation for subsequent analysis. Following these pilots, a total of 274 stakeholders were contacted, 39 Q-sorts for worldviews and pollinator values and 48 Q-sorts for pollinator conservation strategies were completed online, with 38 respondents successfully completing both Q-sorts, resulting in a response rate of approximately 14%. This response rate aligns with typical participation rates observed in online survey-based research, particularly in studies involving specialized stakeholders (e.g., Sheehan, 2001; Saleh & Bista, 2017; Cook et al., 2000). To facilitate the Q-sorting process and data analysis, the QMethod Software was used to administer the Q-sorts online in English.

Stage 3. Quantitative analysis

Analytically, each ranking (Q-sort) represents an individual's 1) worldviews and values of and about pollinators as well as 2) views on effective actions for pollinator conservation. The two datasets with all individual rankings are then analysed separately. The analysis groups participants who rank the statements in a similar manner, reducing the individual Q-sorts to a few profiles that represent distinct perspectives. We used 'qmethod' for R to analyse our data (Zabala, 2014).

Based on the scree plot of unrotated factors and other standard criteria to select the number of factors (e.g. factor Eigen values, factor variances and Humphrey's rule; Watts and Stenner, 2012). On the one hand, we identified four distinct stakeholder profiles (W1–W4), each reflecting different worldviews and values of and about pollinators. On the other hand, we identified four distinct stakeholder profiles (A1–A4) each reflecting pollinator conservation actions.

These profiles are characterized by the statements that most clearly distinguished groups of responses from one another. To arrive to distinguishing statements, factor loadings were examined to determine which participants exemplified each factor most strongly, and factor scores for each statement were calculated to understand how each perspective prioritised or devalued particular statements. Each profile is represented by weighted average scores for each statement. The z-score represents the weighted average score assigned to each statement by participants aligned with a given factor, offering a nuanced view of how strongly each profile supports or opposes particular statements. We used Principal Components Analysis (PCA) and varimax rotation to obtain clearly distinctive perspectives. Since the data are not parametric, the PCA was based on Spearman correlation coefficients. We experimented with other forms of rotation, but a preliminary interpretation of the outcomes of each rotation suggested that a varimax solution was relevant (Akhtar-Danesh, 2017).

Stage 4. Interpretation of results

We interpret the idealised Q-sorts by constructing a narrative for each, summarizing the shared perspectives that define each viewpoint. To do so, we integrated the quantitative results — such as factor loadings, scores, and distinguishing statements — with participants' qualitative explanations provided after the sorting process. Participant narratives helped clarify why certain statements were ranked highly or not, allowing us to contextualize the factors and offer deeper insights into the perspectives identified (Watts and Stenner, 2012). The approach provided both shared and distinguishing perspectives on conservation of nature and pollinators among participants, allowing to better understand and articulate the profiles represented by each factor (Figure 2 and Figure 4; Sup. Mat. Table S.5 & S.6).

3. Results and interpretation

Descriptive statistics of observable characteristics across distinct stakeholder profiles for both worldviews and values (W1-W4) and actions (A1-A4) revealed no consistent patterns (e.g., sector, Table 4.a, Sup. Mat., Table 4.s.).

Q1. What areas of consensus and divergence emerge among key stakeholder worldviews and values on pollinators?

Four profiles reflecting different worldviews and values (W1-W4) about pollinators accounted for 64% of the total variance in responses.

Key distinguishing statements among the W1-W4 profiles, upper part of Figure 1, addressed issues such as lack of data (s37), pesticide necessity (s2), food variety (s8), food waste (s31) and food habits (s30), financial benefits (s32) or usefulness (s20), technology alternative (s5) and technology illusion (s33). Consensus statements (Figure 1, bottom) showed that pollinators are valued for their own sake (s26, s21). Participants strongly rejected replacing wild pollinators (s4), stressing their cultural importance (s13) and role in human nutrition (s9). They also disagreed that wind-pollinated crops are sufficient (s3), or that protecting wild

pollinators in Europe would harm farmers' competitiveness (s14), but also disagreed that wild pollinators extinction may raise food prices (s10).

Figure 1. Ranking of statements and corresponding z-scores relative to other worldview factors. Ordered from most disagreement overall (top) to most consensus (bottom) among perspectives.

The identified perspectives are interpreted as follows (Figure 1, Figure 2): social needs balance (W1); ethical (W2); all-species equality (W3); and human-centred non-intervention (W4).

Figure 2. Interpretation of worldviews on nature and pollinator values

W1- Social needs balance: This perspective emphasised the importance of pollinators in meeting food variety needs and maintaining crop yields. While it acknowledged the role of technology (s5) in compensating for pollinator loss where necessary to improve yield (s6) for human needs, it emphasised the value of pollinators in their own right. Also, the perspective highlighted the ecological significance of pollinators for both plant and animal life. It expressed caution toward the assumption that humans have the right to dominate other life forms, noting that such a view risks unintended ecological consequences and may compromise long-term sustainability. This perspective emphasised that a balanced human–nature relationship is critical for mitigating pollinators declines while supporting socio-economic development.

W2- Ethical: This perspective tended to be nature-centred guided by strong moral concerns (s19, Figure 1), including a rejection of human domination over nature, and viewed pollinators as a web of life-support for other plants and animals. It emphasized the importance of individual

food habits as a means to reduce the pressure of agricultural intensification and other causes of pollinator declines. It viewed the risks associated with pollinator decline as too severe to even run the risk of this happening.

W3 - All-species equality: This perspective acknowledged plural values of pollinators and expressed worldviews grounded in the belief that humans are not separate from, nor superior to, other species, rather in interdependence relationships. It explicitly questioned the perceived dualism between people and nature, rejecting notions of human domination. This perspective did not explicitly endorse the idea that pollinators have a right to exist, it supported pollinator protection regardless of direct utility to humans. This perspective also underscored the physical limits to economic growth on a finite planet and dismissed the assumption that technological innovation alone can resolve complex ecological challenges.

W4 - Human-centred non-intervention: This perspective expressed worldviews rooted in the belief that humans have the right to govern other life forms. It viewed meeting the food demands of a growing global population as a priority and necessity to support increased agricultural productivity. While this perspective acknowledged pollinators' own right, it questioned the adequacy of current data on pollinator decline to justify strong conservation measures. This group also rejected the idea that changing individual food habits is necessary (S30, Figure 1), reflecting a preference for minimal government intervention in consumption patterns and production systems.

Q2. What are the main actions aimed at pollinator conservation that key stakeholders regard as (un)important or (ir)relevant?

Four profiles representing distinct respondents' perspectives on pollinator conservation actions (A1-A4) explained 46.27% of the total variance in responses.

The key distinguishing statements among the A1–A4 profiles (upper section of Figure 3) focused on issues such as the necessity of governmental regulations (e.g., pesticide bans and reductions: s7, s8; elimination of harmful subsidies), the promotion of safer technical solutions (s10), enhanced collaboration and coordination both within and beyond the government

organisations (s35, s37), and increased public awareness (s32, s33, s1, s3). In contrast, the consensus statements (lower section of Figure 2) highlighted the importance of conservation across all governance levels (s29), the provision of incentives for farmers (s34), and increased governmental investment to support the implementation of pollinator-friendly practices. Perspectives on nature and pollinator conservation actions can be interpreted along four distinct orientations: top-down regulations (A1); alternative technical solutions (A2); horizontal coordination and collaboration (A3); bottom-up awareness (A4).

Figure 3. Ranking of statements and corresponding z-scores relative to other action factors. Ordered from most disagreement (top) to most consensus (bottom) among perspectives.

A1 - Top-down regulations: This perspective emphasized the importance of top-down strategies, particularly at all levels of governance (s29). It considered incentives specific to wild pollinators as essential for addressing their decline and oppose the views that measures that benefit honeybees also benefit wild pollinators (s18). This perspective also called for stricter regulatory oversight to prevent greenwashing (e.g., s39) and supported the use of command-and-control instruments embedded within a coherent legal framework across EU member

states. This includes eliminating harmful subsidies (s17), enforcing bans on hazardous pesticides (s7) and disagreed with the need to develop safer pesticides (s10).

A2 – Alternative technical solutions: This perspective expressed a preference for alternative technical solutions to pesticides such as natural pest control (s9) and reduction of pesticides (s8). It advocated for the development of pesticides that are demonstrably safer for human health, non-target species, and the environment (s10). It also supported a complete ban on pesticides (s7), reinforced by legal frameworks (s26), incentives, governance mechanisms, and regulatory measures. Beyond pesticides, this perspective considered effective to ensure that all the impacts of the production of goods and services on nature are taken into account in their price (internalisation of externalities, s16). Conversely, this perspective does not consider dietary changes, such as reducing meat consumption (s5), to be an effective measure.

A3 – Horizontal coordination and collaboration: This perspective emphasized the advancement of science (s24, s22) as the primary pathway to protect pollinators, favouring collaboration (s35), and coordination across sectors and within sector (s37, s20) to address pollinators decline efficiently. While it acknowledged the role of incentives and governance, they highlighted the necessity of economic evaluation (s28) to inform decision-making, but viewed actions such as banning (7) or reducing (s8) pesticide use, polluter-pays (s30), restriction on pollinator-unfriendly imports (s38) and stringent legal framework as an ineffective strategy for pollinator conservation.

A4 - Bottom-up awareness: This identified raising public awareness (s33) as a key element in promoting pollinator conservation, particularly in urban environments. From a precautionary perspective, it advocated for the protection of pollinators, noting the uncertainty surrounding the full consequences of their decline. This perspective emphasised the need to be cautious (s1), Bio-security awareness (s13) and create and preserve nature across all landscapes (s3) — managed, natural, and urban. It also called for increased government investment to support

the implementation of scientific recommendations aimed at safeguarding pollinator populations.

Figure 4. Interpretation of perspectives on nature and pollinator conservation actions

Q3. What is the association between worldviews, values and actions and how can we build on this to improve pollinator conservation?

The statistical cross-analysis of respondents' sorting data indicate how subjective, worldview-based foundations may relate to preferences for conservation actions, which are often framed within rational, effectiveness-driven logic (Figure 5).

		Top-down regulations	Alternative technical solutions	Horizontal coordination and collaboration	Bottom-up awareness	Social needs balance	Ethical	All-species equality	Human-centred non-intervention
		Actions				Worldviews & Values			
		A1	A2	A3	A4	W1	W2	W3	W4
Actions	Top-down regulations	A1	1						
	Alternative technical solutions	A2	0.02	1					
	Horizontal coordination and collaboration	A3	-0.37	-0.32	1				
	Bottom-up awareness	A4	-0.37	-0.15	-0.12	1			
Worldviews & Values	Social needs balance	W1	<u>0.51</u>	0.31	-0.26	-0.19	1		
	Ethical	W2	-0.02	<u>0.3</u>	-0.15	<u>0.3</u>	-0.13	1	
	All-species equality	W3	<u>0.37</u>	0.18	<u>-0.41</u>	0.11	0.1	-0.20	1
	Human-centred non-intervention	W4	<u>-0.57</u>	-0.24	<u>0.71</u>	-0.24	-0.44	-0.32	-0.43

Figure 5. Correlation between worldviews, values and actions perspectives

The correlations suggest some patterns between preferences for pollinator conservation actions and worldviews and values. The *human-centred non-intervention* worldview (W4) aligned strongly with *horizontal coordination and collaboration* type of actions (A3) (0.71) and opposed to *top-down regulations* (A1) (-0.57). In contrast, *societal needs balance* (W1) and *all-species equality* worldviews (W3) associated positively with *top-down regulations* (A1) (0.51 and 0.37, respectively), with the latter also displaying a negative correlation with *horizontal coordination and collaboration* (A2) (-0.41). The *ethical* worldview (W2) associated moderately with both *alternative technical solutions* (A2) and *bottom-up awareness* (A4) (0.30 each). These patterns show that support for specific conservation approaches may vary with underlying values and worldviews.

4. Discussion

This study captures how worldviews and values of key stakeholders intersect with policy preferences. Although some perspectives reflect well-established patterns in conservation thinking, others reveal configurations of values and action preferences that are less documented, especially in relation to pollinator-focused debates. This suggests the need for further investigation into context-specific framings, particularly as global conservation policy shifts toward more inclusive and multifunctional governance models.

4.1. Worldviews and top-down versus horizontal governance

Individuals aligned with the *social needs balance* perspective (W1) expressed a positive correlation with top-down regulations (0.51). This may indicate a preference for institutional intervention framed within a pragmatic, socio-economic rationale. The *ethical* perspective (W2) showed a less pronounced negative correlation with top-down (-0.02) and horizontal (-0.15) governance. It was rather moderately aligned with both *alternative technical solutions* and *bottom-up awareness* actions (0.30 for each), indicating a more flexible or integrative stance. These individuals may support a range of conservation actions, provided they align with underlying moral principles.

One notable finding concerns the net contrast between *human-centred non-intervention* (W4) and *all-species equality* (W3) worldviews and values, particularly regarding governance approach (Figure 5). *The all-species equality* (W3) showed a moderate positive correlation with top-down interventions (0.37), but a negative correlation with horizontal coordination (-0.41). This suggests a value orientation grounded in ethical concern for non-human life that nonetheless favors directive, rules-based governance rather than inclusive or collaborative models. In contrast, the *human-centred non-intervention* perspective (W4) was strongly and positively correlated with preferences for *horizontal coordination and collaborative* (0.71), while showing a significant negative correlation with top-down regulations (-0.57). This strong polarity underscores a worldview that values autonomy, local engagement, and potentially informal or decentralised solutions, while displaying resistance toward hierarchical or state-imposed measures. Overall, these results challenge the assumption that moral focused worldviews and values (e.g. species equality, W3/ethical, W2) necessarily prioritise deliberative modes of governance, including collaboration and coordination. Perhaps, this is due to necessary trade-offs to conserve pollinators, asymmetries in power or information among key stakeholders. Once again, collaborative and coordinated conservation measures can be difficult to implement given the wide diversity of worldviews among stakeholders (e.g., human dominance, see s1, Figure 1).

4.2. Preferences over pesticides

Worldviews on the necessity of pesticides (s2, Figure 1) and preferences for actions aimed at reducing their use (s7, s8, s9, s10, s30; Figure 3) varied considerably, as reflected in the literature (e.g. Bloom et al., 2021, Nicholls et al., 2020). For instance, actions related to pesticide bans (s7) were supported across *top-down regulations* (A1) and *alternative technical solutions* (A2), but preferences for other actions regarding pesticides varied. For A2, pesticide reduction (s8) and safer pesticide (s10) appeared relevant as primarily embedded in a broader moral logic and concerns for efficiency and technical risk management. A1, however, disregards pesticide-reduction or safer pesticides due to perceived ecological consequences (Figure 5). Also, A1 indicates discomfort with industrial pollution and concerns with human-nature relations. In contrast, A3 indicated discomfort with any actions targeting pesticides (ban, s7 or reduction s8), polluters paying (s30) and even effectiveness of alternatives such as natural pest control (s9). This suggests that although pesticide reduction may be widely endorsed as a conservation measure, it is not univocally understood and accepted — it carries distinct meanings within different worldviews.

However, our sample could influence both the salience of certain statements (e.g., pesticide management, governance mechanisms) and the coherence of sorting patterns, given their high level of education and exposure to environmental or agricultural issues. Also, the interpretation of specific items — particularly those related to pesticide use and governance preferences, may carry contextual meanings not fully captured in the study.

4.3. Comparison of perspectives with earlier literature

The perspectives identified in this study align in part with those found in previous Q-methodology research on conservation, values and stakeholder framings (Chan et al., 2016). However, several distinctions suggest context-specific orientations and possible evolution in public discourse around pollinators and biodiversity governance. Perspectives emphasizing top-down regulatory governance are consistent with findings from prior studies on nature conservation. For instance, Raymond and Kenter (2016) and Fischer et al. (2021) similarly reported the presence of actor groups advocating for institutional authority, standardised rules,

and strong state-led responses to environmental degradation. These perspectives often align with a belief in science-led management and precautionary regulation, reflecting trust in formal institutions as central agents in conservation efforts (Drivdal et al., 2020). The presence of a collaborative governance-oriented profile (A3), which prioritizes horizontal coordination, stakeholder inclusion, and shared responsibility, also mirrors findings from studies emphasizing deliberative and participatory approaches (e.g., Ives & Kendal, 2014; Orchard-Webb et al., 2016). This perspective reflects an orientation toward multi-actor governance frameworks and often resonates with the principles of adaptive co-management or community-based conservation, particularly in socio-ecological systems where local knowledge and relational values are emphasized (Salomon et al., 2023; Robinson, 2011; Vucetich et al., 2018). However, our study also identifies a relatively distinct, human-centered and non-intervention perspective, which has received limited attention in previous Q-studies on biodiversity. While echoes of this stance appear in literature describing laissez-faire or technocratic skepticism (e.g., Buijs et al., 2012), the strong correlation between this worldview and preferences for collaborative over regulatory approaches (as seen in the results) suggests a more coherent and under-recognized position. This group appears to value personal autonomy, natural resilience, and informal coordination, positioning top-down regulatory as potentially disruptive rather than efficient.

4.4. Implications for policies and practices

Our results suggest that support for specific conservation interventions may be shaped by deeper normative orientations, and that governance preferences are not randomly distributed but rather cohere with broader ethical and socio-political beliefs.

Understanding the relationships between worldviews and preferred conservation actions provides valuable insight for the design and implementation of pollinator conservation strategies. Rather than assuming uniform support for particular policy measures, this study highlights the importance of tailoring interventions to resonate with the distinct values and governance preferences of different stakeholder groups (Gemmill-Herren et al., 2021; Marselle et al., 2021). For example, conservation initiatives aimed at those who prioritise personal

autonomy or who are skeptical of state-led regulation may be more successful if framed around collaborative processes, knowledge co-production, or locally driven coordination mechanisms, which align with the W4 profile. Conversely, approaches targeting individuals with strong egalitarian or institutional trust orientations may benefit from emphasizing scientific authority, legal mandates, and universal norms, as preferred by W1 and W3.

Furthermore, the findings suggest that certain policy tools, such as pesticide regulation, may receive cross-cutting support, but for different reasons. Some respondents may view pesticide reduction as a necessary technical fix, while others perceive it as a reflection of deeper ethical commitments. Recognizing this heterogeneity can help craft more inclusive messaging and coalition-building around specific conservation actions.

Overall, integrating an understanding of value-action linkages into conservation planning may enhance the social legitimacy, uptake, and durability of pollinator conservation measures across diverse governance contexts.

5. Conclusion

This study examines how key stakeholder groups in Europe understand, value and approach pollinator conservation. The findings reveal that conservation preferences are not solely based on instrumental reasoning or effectiveness-driven logic, but are closely tied to underlying worldviews and relational values. By mapping these diverse perspectives and their associated governance preferences, the study underscores the importance of integrating ethical, cultural, and social dimensions into pollinator policy and practice. Recognizing this plurality is essential for designing conservation strategies that are both ecologically effective and socially legitimate.

Future studies might benefit from integrating qualitative follow-up interviews to unpack such interpretive nuance. Additionally, while this study examined correlations between values and action preferences, it did not assess how these perspectives translate into actual behavior or policy engagement. Also, this research focused on pollinator conservation as a case study, but a similar approach could be applied to other domains of biodiversity governance to test the stability and variability of identified perspectives. Cross-cultural comparisons or longitudinal

studies would be especially valuable in assessing whether these worldview-action configurations are context-dependent or reflect broader trends in conservation thinking. Future research could explore the extent to which these value-action alignments shape participation in conservation initiatives, influence public support for specific policies, or shift over time in response to changing environmental or social conditions.

6. Reference

- Agnoletti, M., Emanuelli, F. 2016. Biocultural Diversity and Landscape in Europe: Framing the Issue. In: Agnoletti, M., Emanuelli, F. (eds) Biocultural Diversity in Europe. Environmental History, vol 5. Springer, Cham.
- Akhtar-Danesh, N. 2017. An overview of the statistical techniques in Q methodology: Is there a better way of doing Q analysis?. *Operant Subjectivity*, 38(3/4).
- Brown, SR. 1980. Political subjectivity: Applications of Q methodology in political science. New Haven and London. Available at <http://qmethod.org/papers/Brown-1980-PoliticalSubjectivity.pdf>: Yale University Press.
- Bloom, E.H., Bauer, D.M., Kaminski, A., Kaplan, I. and Szendrei, Z., 2021. Socioecological factors and farmer perceptions impacting pesticide use and pollinator conservation on cucurbit farms. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, p.672981.
- Buijs, A. E., Arts, B. J. M., Elands, B. H. M., & Lengkeek, J. 2012. Beyond environmental frames: The social representation and cultural resonance of nature in conflicts over a Dutch woodland. *Geoforum*, 43(3), 554–565.
- Chan K, Balvanera P, Benessaiah K, Chapman M, Díaz S, Gómez-Baggethun E, et al. 2016. 'Why protect nature? Rethinking values and the environment.' *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*.;113(6):1462-1465. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1525002113
- Chan, K., Gould, K.R., and Pascual, U. 2018. 'Editorial overview: Relational values: what are they, and what's the fuss about?'. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, Volume 35, Pages A1-A7. ISSN 1877-3435, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.11.003>.

- Cook, C., Heath, F., & Thompson, R. L. 2000. A meta-analysis of response rates in web-or internet-based surveys. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 60(6), 821-836.
- Dicks, L. V., Breeze, T. D., Ngo, H. T., Senapathi, D., et al. 2021. 'A global-scale expert assessment of drivers and risks associated with pollinator decline.' *Nature Ecology & Evolution*. Drivdal, L. and van der Sluijs, J.P., 2021. Pollinator conservation requires a stronger and broader application of the precautionary principle. *Current opinion in insect science*, 46, pp.95-105.
- Dupré, L., Fortier A., et Alphandéry P., 2021, Abeilles - Le sacrifice des pollinisateurs, *Vocabulaire critique & spéculatif des transitions*.
<https://vocabularyrestransitions.fr/article-17>
- Fisher, D. R., Jasny, L., Redmond, J., & Heaume, F. 2021. Environmental governance. In *Handbook of Environmental Sociology* (pp. 333-353). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Gemmill-Herren, B., Garibaldi, L.A., Kremen, C. and Ngo, H.T., 2021. Building effective policies to conserve pollinators: translating knowledge into policy. *Current opinion in insect science*, 46, pp.64-71.
- Klain, S. C., Olmsted, P., Chan, K. M., & Satterfield, T. 2017. Relational values resonate broadly and differently than intrinsic or instrumental values, or the New Ecological Paradigm. *PLOS ONE*, 12(8), e0183962.
- IPBES. 2016. 'The assessment report on pollinators, pollination and food production: summary for policymakers.' Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services.
- IPBES. 2019. 'The global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services: Summary for policy makers.' Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services.
- IPBES. 2022. 'Chapter 2: Conceptualizing the diverse values of nature and their contributions to people.' Methodological Assessment Report on the Diverse Values and Valuation of

Nature of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany.

- IPBES. 2024. Summary for Policymakers of the Thematic Assessment Report on the Underlying Causes of Biodiversity Loss and the Determinants of Transformative Change and Options for Achieving the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. O'Brien, K., Garibaldi, L., Agrawal, A., Bennett, E., Biggs, R., Calderón Contreras, R., Carr, E., Frantzeskaki, N., Gosnell, H., Gurung, J., Lambertucci, S., Leventon, J., Liao, C., Reyes García, V., Shannon, L., Villasante, S., Wickson, F., Zinngrebe, Y., and Perianin, L. (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382230>
- Ives, C. D., & Kendal, D. 2014. The role of social values in the management of ecological systems. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 144, 67–72
- Jax, K., Melania Calestani, Chan, K. M., Eser, U., Keune, H., Muraca, B., O'Brien, L., Potthast, T., Voget-Kleschin, L., Wittmer, H. 2018. 'Caring for nature matters: a relational approach for understanding nature's contributions to human well-being.' *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 35: 22-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2018.10.009>.
- Kinneen, L.K., Potts, S.G. & Senapathi, D. 2022. 'Safeguard stakeholder mapping report.' Deliverable D7.1, EU Horizon 2020 Safeguard Project, Grant agreement No 101003476.
- Klain, S. C., Olmsted, P., Chan, K. M., & Satterfield, T. 2017. Relational values resonate broadly and differently than intrinsic or instrumental values, or the New Ecological Paradigm. *PLOS ONE*, 12(8), e0183962.
- Lautenbach, S., Seppelt, R., Liebscher, J., and Dormann, C. F. 2012. 'Spatial and temporal trends of global pollination benefit.' *PloS One*, 7(4): e35954.
- Lo, A. Y., & Spash, C. L. 2013. Deliberative monetary valuation: in search of a democratic and value plural approach to environmental policy. *Journal of economic surveys*, 27(4), 768-789.

- Marselle, M.R., Turbe, A., Shwartz, A., Bonn, A. and Colléony, A., 2021. Addressing behavior in pollinator conservation policies to combat the implementation gap. *Conservation Biology*, 35(2), pp.610-622.
- MEA. 2005. Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis. Island Press, Washington DC.
- Muradian, R. and Gómez-Baggethun, E. 2021. Beyond ecosystem services and nature's contributions: Is it time to leave utilitarian environmentalism behind? *Ecological Economics*, Volume 185, 107038. Nicholls, A.A., Epstein, G.B. and Colla, S.R., 2020. Understanding public and stakeholder attitudes in pollinator conservation policy development. *Environmental science & policy*, 111, pp.27-34.
- Orchard-Webb J., Kenter Jasper O., Bryce Ros, Church Andrew. 2016. Deliberative Democratic Monetary Valuation to implement the Ecosystem Approach, *Ecosystem Services*, Volume 21, Part B, Pages 308-318, ISSN 2212-0416, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.09.005>.
- Potts, S. G., Imperatriz-Fonseca, V., Ngo, H. T., Aizen, M. A., Biesmeijer, J. C., Breeze, T. D., Dicks, L. V., Garibaldi, L. A., Hill, R., Settele, J. & Vanbergen, A. J. 2016. 'Safeguarding pollinators and their values to human well-being.' *Nature*, 540, 220–229.
- Raymond, C. M., & Kenter, J. O. 2016. Transcendental values and the valuation and management of ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services*, 21, 241-257.
- Robinson, J.G., 2011. Ethical pluralism, pragmatism, and sustainability in conservation practice. *Biological Conservation*, 144(3), pp.958-965.
- Saleh, A., & Bista, K. 2017. Examining factors impacting online survey response rates in educational research: Perceptions of graduate students. *Journal of Multidisciplinary evaluation*, 13(29), 63-74.
- Salomon, A., Okamoto, D., Wilson, K., Happynook, H., , W., Mack, W., Davidson, S., Guujaaw, G., Humchitt, W., Happynook, T., Cox, W., Gillette, H., Christiansen, N., Dragon, D., Kobluk, H., Lee, L., Tinker, M., Silver, J., Armitage, D., McKechnie, I., MacNeil, A., Hillis, D., Muhl, E., Gregr, E., Commander, C., & Augustine, A. 2023. Disrupting and diversifying the values, voices and governance principles that shape biodiversity science and management.

Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, 378.
<https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2022.0196>.

Sheehan, K. B. 2001. E-mail survey response rates: A review. *Journal of computer-mediated communication*, 6(2), JCMC621.

Scott, J. 2000. Rational Choice Theory. In G. Browning, A. Halcli, & F. Webster (Eds.), *Understanding Contemporary Society: Theories of the Present* (pp. 126–138). Sage Publications.

Simon, H. 1947. *Administrative behavior*. New York: Free Press.

Stephenson, W. 1953. *The study of behavior; Q-technique and its methodology*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Subiza-Pérez, M., Zabala, A., Groten, D., Vozmediano, L., Juan, C. S., & Ibarluzea, J. 2023. Waste-to-energy risk perception typology: health, politics and environmental impacts. *Journal of Risk Research*, 26(10), 1101–1118.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2023.2259402>

Uwingabire, Z., Gallai, N., 2024. Impacts of degraded pollination ecosystem services on global food security and nutrition. *Ecol. Econ.* 217, 108068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2023.108068>

Uwingabire, Z., Vanbergen, A. J., Damiens, F. L. P., Breeze, T. D., van der Wal, R., & Young, J. C. 2025. Worldviews and values of key societal actors influencing decision-making around nature: The case of wild pollinator conservation in Europe. *People and Nature*, 00,1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.70035>

Van Born, R., Lenders, R., Groot, W., & Huijsman, E. 2001. The new biophilia: An exploration of visions of nature in Western countries. *Environmental Conservation*, 28(1), 65-75.
doi:10.1017/S0376892901000066

Vanbergen, A.J., the Insect Pollinators Initiative. 2013. Threats to an ecosystem service: pressures on pollinators. *Front. Ecol. Environ.*, 11, pp. 251-259.
<https://doi.org/10.1890/120126>

Vucetich, J.A., Burnham, D., Macdonald, E.A., Bruskotter, J.T., Marchini, S., Zimmermann, A. and Macdonald, D.W., 2018. Just conservation: What is it and should we pursue it?. *Biological Conservation*, 221, pp.23-33.

Watts S, Stenner P. 2012. Doing Q Methodological Research: Theory, Method & Interpretation. London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Zabala A. 2014. qmethod: A package to explore human perspectives using Q methodology. *The R Journal*; 6: 163:173.

Zabala, A., Pascual, U. 2016. Bootstrapping Q Methodology to Improve the Understanding of Human Perspectives. *PLoS ONE* 11(2): e0148087. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0148087